

RESEARCH ON THE STIFFNESS OF COMPOSITE PIPES UNDER STATIC FATIGUE AND CYCLIC FATIGUE

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Keywords: composite pipes, static fatigue, cyclic fatigue

ABSTRACT

Composite pipes have the advantages of corrosion resistance and lightweight, and are widely used in pressure and non-pressure water supply, drainage and sewerage engineering. As a buried pipe, it needs to resist the dead load, such as soil load, and live load, such as vehicle load. The static fatigue and cyclic fatigue act simultaneously on composite pipes. In order to ensure safety, it is necessary to study the stiffness of composite pipes under static fatigue and cyclic fatigue. The stiffness of composite pipes under static fatigue and cyclic fatigue are researched on the experiments. The diameter of composite pipes specimen is 200 mm. Two parallel steel plates are used to fix the composite pipe under different deflection to simulate the static fatigue. The cyclic fatigue is simulated by applying different cyclic displacement amplitude to the composite pipes specimen with a fatigue testing machine. The stiffness of composite pipes is measured at a different time interval or at different cyclic numbers, and the law of the stiffness degradation is obtained. The relationship of the stiffness degradation between the static fatigue and cyclic fatigue is also obtained.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, composite materials have received more and more attention in the fields of aerospace, transportation, construction, machinery and industry because of its advantages of higher strength-to-weight ratio, longer durability, and better environmental resistance compared with metal materials. Compared with metal materials, composite pipes are less prone to corrosion, rust and scaling. It is an advantage of composite pipes for long-term service. During the long-term service, as a resin-based composite material, with the increases of service time, the damage induces by alternating loading, the mechanical properties of the Glass Fiber Reinforced Plastics (GFRP) pipes will be weakened, the ring stiffness will decrease, which may lead to failure of the GFRP pipes. Under the initial internal pressure of constant normal use, the GFRP pipes may fail after a certain period of time. Research on creep of composite materials. M. Farshad^[1] uses ADAP analysis to obtain a transition zone for the double logarithmic curve of laminated pipes under long-term hydrostatic strength. And after the transition zone, long-term performance drops rapidly with time. H. Faria^[2] proposed a method that could be used for 1000 hour test instead of 10000 hours for a long-term performance prediction. R.M. Guedes^[3-5] used the maximum strain criterion combined with experimental analysis to conclude that the logarithmic relationship between long-term performance and time is an open-down parabola. The fibers and matrix of the resin-based composite material are deformed as an entirety when the material creeps, and the stress between the fibers is transmitted through the resin of the base material. The microstructure of the entire material has not changed. J. Raghavan^[6] proposed a model incorporating a modified thermal activation theory is presented to model and predict creep of polymer composites. And concluded that the reinforcing carbon fibers do not alter the creep mechanism but do alter the creep behavior of the epoxy matrix, resulting in reductions in creep rate and in the magnitude of creep.

Research on fatigue of composite materials. W. Hwang^[7] found that cumulative damage model could be classified as damage models defined by the number of cycles and material characteristic variables and then he proposed three different fatigue damage models using fatigue modulus and resultant strain. Based on the stiffness degradation rule of composite materials under fatigue loading, F.

Wu ^[8] analyzed the factors related to fatigue damage development of composites, defined a phenomenological fatigue damage model described by material stiffness degradation and presented a phenomenological fatigue damage model. Combining nonlinear residual strength and residual stiffness models with the recently improved Puck's failure theory which includes the in situ strength effect, H. Dong ^[9] developed a new fatigue failure theory for multidirectional fiber-reinforced composite laminates with an arbitrary stacking sequence, which can predict the fatigue life, residual strength and residual failure envelope of fiber-reinforced composite laminates under multidirectional loadings. By computationally and experimentally, R. Tang ^[10] proved that damage caused by tensile loading in fiber reinforced polymeric composite laminates may induce only minor variations in the longitudinal stiffness, thereby rendering this stiffness a poor measure for estimating the residual strength of such materials.

Research on long-term performance of GFRP pipes. N. Tarakcioglu ^[11, 12] investigated the fatigue behavior of $[\pm 55]_3$ filament wound composite pipes with a surface crack under alternating internal pressure, fatigue behavior of filament wound composite pipes under alternating internal pressure. A. Samanci ^[13, 14] investigated fatigue damage behavior of $[\pm 75]_3$ filament wound composite pipes with a surface crack under alternating internal pressure, the fatigue behavior of $[\pm 45]_3$ filament-wound composite pipes with a surface crack under alternating internal pressure.

From this paper, a relationship of the stiffness degradation between the static fatigue and cyclic fatigue would be obtained. This research mainly includes:

1. Long-term performance test of constant displacement of GFRP pipes.
2. Based on the experimental data, establish a predictive expression for the long-term stiffness of the GFRP pipes.
3. Basic fatigue test of GFRP pipes.
4. Establish a prediction formula for long-term ring stiffness based on fatigue test data.
5. Fatigue test method for establishing long-term performance of GFRP pipes by comparative analysis.

2 TEST

2.1 Test specimens

Using a fixed-length winding type, making GFRP pipe specimens from mechanical equipment. In this paper, using three kinds of winding pattern to make specimens. Respectively, marking hoop winding $[90]_4$ as type A, helical winding $[\pm 58]_2$ as type B, hoop-helical combined winding $[90/\pm 58/90]$ as type C. The size of the test specimens was taken as the thickness of 2 mm, length of 20 mm and a diameter of 200 mm. The test specimens were naturally cured in the first day, heated and cured by an infrared baking sheet in the next day. All three kinds' type are used Jiangsu Fullmark Chemicals co., LTD. FL889 resin and Chongqing international composite materials co., LTD ER winding yarn. The specimens are shown in Figure 1, and the composition are showed in Table 1.

Figure 1: GFRP pipes specimens.

Type	Glass fiber(%)	Resin(%)
Type A	60.53	39.47
Type B	59.77	40.23
Type C	61.83	38.17

Table 1: Content of GFRP pipes specimens.

2.2 Ring stiffness test

An Instron 5848 Micro Tester (Figure 2) has been used for the stiffness test. According to ISO 9969:2007 Thermoplastics Pipes - Determination of Ring Stiffness, the load corresponding to a 3% deformation in the direction of the pipe diameter has been measured. The compression rate of the GFRP pipe was determined in the range of (5 ± 0.25) mm min⁻¹. This test takes 5 mm min⁻¹, and pipe's stiffness is calculated as follows:

$$S = (0.0186 + 0.025 \cdot \frac{y}{d}) \cdot \frac{F}{Ly} \times 10^6 \quad (1)$$

F: Load at 3.0 % deformation of GFRP pipe (kN),

L: Length of GFRP pipe (mm),

y: Deflection at 3.0 % deformation of GFRP pipe (mm),

d: Inner diameter of GFRP pipe (mm),

S: Ring stiffness (kN/m²)

The formula could be further simplified to:

$$S = 0.01935 \cdot \frac{F}{Ly} \times 10^6 \quad (2)$$

Figure 2: Instron 5848 Micro Tester and Ring stiffness test

2.3 Static fatigue test

In order to accurately control the constant displacement of the specimens and reduce the error caused by the specimens' device, the loading device (Figure 3) of the test was specially designed and customized.

Dividing the specimens of type A, type B and type C into 3 groups, respectively. The constant displacement of group A-1, B-1 and C-1 are controlled to 10mm (5% of diameter). The constant displacement of group A-2, B-2 and C-2 are controlled to 20mm (10% of diameter). The constant displacement of group A-3, B-3 and C-3 are controlled to 30mm (15% of diameter).

Step 1 – Designed the loading device according to the predetermined size, number the specimens and measure the size of each specimens. Test the initial ring stiffness of specimens.

Step 2 – Apply a displacement to each group of specimens as the loading device customized constant displacement.

Step 3 – At regular intervals, the specimen is taken from each group contains for the ring stiffness test. To avoid the influence on the stiffness of the specimens causing by excessive unloading and loading, the test should ensure that the specimens are loaded for a sufficient period of time, then unloading for the ring stiffness test.

Step 4 – Repetition of the Steps 2 and 3 at regular intervals.

Figure 3: The loading device and Static fatigue test

Figure 4: The QBS-100 electro-hydraulic servo fatigue testing machine and cyclic fatigue test

2.4 Cyclic fatigue test

The QBS-100 electro-hydraulic servo fatigue testing machine (Figure 4) was used in the cyclic fatigue test.

Dividing all specimens into 3 groups like Static fatigue test.

Group A-1, B-1 and C-1 takes the maximum displacement as 10(mm) (5% of diameter), the initial displacement as 6(mm), the amplitude as 4(mm). Group A-2, B-2 and C-2 takes the maximum displacement as 20(mm) (10 % of diameter), the initial displacement as 16(mm), the amplitude as 4(mm). Group A-3, B-3 and C-3 takes the maximum displacement as 30(mm) (15 % of diameter), the initial displacement as 26(mm), the amplitude as 4(mm).

Step 1 – Test the initial ring stiffness of specimens.

Step 2 – The alternating displacement fatigue test. Take the specimen that have been completed on ring stiffness test to alternating displacement fatigue test and set the initial displacement for each group. The amplitude is set to -4(mm) ("- " means pressure), the frequency is set to 3(Hz), the cycle time is set to 100000, and the selected compression waveform is sine wave.

Step 3- After the specimen reaches the setting number of cycles, the fatigue tester would be stopped and the specimen would be removed for the ring stiffness test.

Step 4- Repetition of the Steps 2 and 3 until one million cycles and the corresponding stiffness test are completed, then proceed test of the next specimen.

2 DATA

3.1 Data of static fatigue test

3.1.1 Double logarithmic linear fitting of stiffness and time

The data of static fatigue test could be used for Equation 2, and the stiffness of each group would be obtained.

In this paper, a double logarithmic model would be used for the data analysis. The ring stiffness and time of specimens were taken logarithmically on the coordinates, and a linear fitting was performed. As follows,

$$y = a + bx \quad (3)$$

y: Logarithm of ring stiffness, $y = \log_{10}(S)$, the unit of S is kN/m^2 ,

x: Logarithm of time, $x = \log_{10}(t)$, the unit of t is hour.

Using OriginPro8 for a double logarithmic linear fitting for stiffness of each group. And the double logarithmic linear fitting curve are shown in Figure 5, Figure 6 and Figure 7.

Figure 5: Double logarithmic linear fitting for type A of static fatigue test

Figure 6: Double logarithmic linear fitting for type B of static fatigue test

Figure 7: Double logarithmic linear fitting for type C of static fatigue test

Through the double logarithmic linear fitting operation above-described, the corresponding functional relationship of each group could be obtained as well. The specific expressions are shown in the Table 2.

Constant displacement	Type A	Type B	Type C
5%	$y=3.34381-0.01565x$	$y=3.42966-0.02502x$	$y=3.24391-0.02726x$
10%	$y=3.36204-0.02127x$	$y=3.42089-0.03215x$	$y=3.25968-0.02969x$
15%	$y=3.35803-0.02258x$	$y=3.33394-0.04259x$	$y=3.25759-0.03723x$

Table 2: Log-log linear fitting expression of static fatigue test

3.1.2 Establishment of long-term stiffness prediction expression

According to the double logarithmic linear fitting result expression of each type in Table 2. The ring stiffness of 50 years under the constant deflection of 5%, 10% and 15% of type A could be obtained respectively. Select the Poly2D model for surface fitting. The expression for fitting surface is:

$$z = z_0 + ax + by + cx^2 + dy^2 + fxy \quad (4)$$

z : The ring stiffness reduction rate, $z = \frac{S_0 - S}{S_0} \times 100\%$,

x : Serve time, years,

y : Ratio of constant deflection to diameter, %.

Figure 8: Nonlinear surface fitting for type A of static fatigue test

Nonlinear surface fitting expression of static fatigue test:

$$z_1 = 0.63218x_1 + 2.17431y_1 - 0.01018x_1^2 - 0.08443y_1^2 + 0.00568x_1y_1 \quad (5)$$

3.2 Data of cyclic fatigue test

3.2.1 Double logarithmic linear fitting of stiffness and cycle number

The data of cyclic fatigue test could be used for Equation 2, and the stiffness of each group would be obtained.

In this paper, a double logarithmic model would be used for the data analysis. The ring stiffness and time of specimens were taken logarithmically on the coordinates, and a linear fitting was performed. As follows,

$$y = a + bx \quad (6)$$

y : Logarithm of ring stiffness, $y = \log_{10}(S)$,

x : Logarithm of time, $x = \log_{10}(N)$.

Using OriginPro8 for a double logarithmic linear fitting for stiffness of each group. And the double logarithmic linear fitting curve are shown in Figure 9, Figure 10 and Figure 11.

Figure 9: Double logarithmic linear fitting for type A of cyclic fatigue test

Figure: 10 Double logarithmic linear fitting for type B of cyclic fatigue test

Through the double logarithmic linear fitting operation above-described, the corresponding functional relationship of each group could be obtained as well. The specific expressions are shown in the Table 3.

Initial displacement	Type A	Type B	Type C
5%	$y=3.41124-0.00444x$	$y=3.38491-0.00970x$	$y=3.38015-0.00664x$
10%	$y=3.39295-0.00831x$	$y=3.41128-0.01287x$	$y=3.36527-0.01248x$
15%	$y=3.40959-0.01037x$	$y=3.42872-0.01802x$	$y=3.38894-0.01809x$

Table 3: Log-log linear fitting result expression of cyclic fatigue test

Figure 11: Double logarithmic linear fitting for type C of cyclic fatigue test

3.2.2 Establish high-period stiffness prediction expression

According to the double logarithmic linear fitting result expression of each type in Table 3. The ring stiffness of 5×10^6 cycles under the maximum deflection of 5%, 10% and 15% of type A could be obtained respectively. Select the Poly2D model for surface fitting. The expression for fitting surface is:

$$z = z_0 + ax + by + cx^2 + dy^2 + fxy \quad (7)$$

z : The ring stiffness reduction rate, %,

x : Number of cycles, $\times 10^5$,

y : Ratio of maximum deflection to diameter, %.

Figure 12: Nonlinear surface fitting for type A of cyclic fatigue test
Nonlinear surface fitting expression of cyclic fatigue test:

$$z_2 = 0.22188x_2 + 0.84221y_2 - 0.00466x_2^2 - 0.01842y_2^2 + 0.00923x_2y_2 \quad (8)$$

3.3 The static fatigue and cyclic fatigue

Comparing Equations (5) and (8), the variable x_1 is a quantity of time, and the variable x_2 is a quantity related to time. Assuming that $x_2=kx_1$, the increase rate of ring stiffness reduction rate could be obtained by taking the derivative of z_1 and z_2 to x_1 .

Static fatigue test:

$$z_1' = 0.63218 - 0.02036x_1 + 0.00568y_1 \quad (9)$$

Cyclic fatigue test:

$$z_2' = 0.22188k - 0.00932k^2x_1 + 0.00923ky_2 \quad (10)$$

To obtain that under the same deflection, the increase rate of ring stiffness reduction rate for static fatigue and the increase rate of ring stiffness reduction rate for cyclic fatigue are equal, $z_1' = z_2'$.

Assuming that $y_1=y_2=a$:

$$(0.00923k^2 - 0.02036)x_1 + 0.63218 - 0.22188k + 0.00568a - 0.00923ka = 0 \quad (11)$$

lead to

$$0.00923k^2 - 0.02036 = 0 \quad (12)$$

and

$$0.63218 - 0.22188k + 0.00568a - 0.00923ka = 0 \quad (13)$$

Coupling Equations (12) and (13):

$$\begin{cases} k = 1.485 \\ a = 37.71 \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

It could be obtained that while the ratio of constant deflection to diameter and the ratio of maximum deflection to diameter are 37.71%, the increase rate of ring stiffness reduction rate for static fatigue and cyclic fatigue are equal. In this case, the relationship between the service time of static fatigue t (years) and the number of cycles N of cyclic fatigue could be :

$$N = 1.485 \times 10^5 t \quad (15)$$

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, basis on static fatigue test and cyclic fatigue test of different type and different deflection, the equation of variation of the ring stiffness is obtained.

(1) The ring stiffness has a similar trend in static fatigue and cyclic fatigue.

(2) For hoop winding GFRP pipes, while the ratio of constant deflection to diameter and the ratio of maximum deflection to diameter are 37.71%, the increase rate of ring stiffness reduction rate for static fatigue and cyclic fatigue are equal.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Financially supported by the Fundamental Research Funds for the Central Universities (WUT: 2018IB001), self-determined and innovative research funds of WUT (2019B016), National High-tech R&D Program (863 Program) (2013AA031306).

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